

Strategic International Business Management

Abstract

The paper looks at a multinational company Tesco PLC. which is a retail company based in the United Kingdom. Tesco is multinational company that operates in many countries around the world and it is among the leading retail companies in the world. As part of its expansion strategies, the company has been working hard to expand its markets in many countries as possible. The paper herein looks at the possibility of Tesco's expansion to three countries which are Singapore, Latvia and Taiwan. The company wants to expand to one of these countries and hence the paper looks at the macro-environmental factors that may affect the operation of Tesco in these countries as shown in the Appendix section of the paper. After a brief analysis of the political, environmental and the economic factors that may affect business in these countries, Singapore comes as the best option. Singapore is the best option due to its political stability, technological status, and its expected economic growth in the next five to ten years. A further analysis of the opportunities of the threats of Tesco in exploring the new market is done using the 5-forces analysis. Section three of this paper looks at the competitiveness of the organization using the VRIO analysis method. Finally, section four looks at the entry methods that Tesco can use to enter the Singapore market to make maximum profits.

Introduction

Tesco is a British-based multinational retailer operating in various countries around the world. The company has its headquarters in Welwyn Garden City, England in the United Kingdom. Tesco is among the largest retailers in the world coming at number three

among the world's most major retailers. Currently, the company is operating in twelve countries across the world and is also working on new strategies to get into new global markets by getting access to new markets. The Tesco Company has a long history dating in the 1920s when it was started in London by its founder Jack Cohen who began selling groceries from a stall in the city of London. Jack later introduced the first own-brand in 1934 which he called the Tesco Tea and later renamed the company to Tesco. The Tesco tea worked well, and Jack later bought land and expanded his shop offering the first self-service shop in the history of London in 1940s. The company continued to grow steadily over the years the 1930s through to 1950s when they opened their first supermarket with a variety of products. The company then started going global in the 1990s and later online in the 2000s or the internet era. The company has continued to explore various markets across the world where it has succeeded to set up its stores, and it has also managed to get significant income from the new markets.

Comparing the three markets Latvia, Singapore and Taiwan the best choice of the market for TESCO could be in Singapore putting into consideration the multiple favorable macro environmental factors that could be plowed in the area. Being a multinational company that mainly retails food and non-food products, it also offers insurance, mobile, hardware, and finance services.

Section 1 (A deeper analysis of the selected market)

The macro environmental factors that could influence the sustainability of Tesco in Singapore could be the political factors, economic factors, social factors, technological factors environmental factors and the legislative factors.

Political factors

Since TESCO operates worldwide, global political factors such as legislative acts, country's stability, and tax rates could greatly influence the performance of the company. The ongoing financial instabilities worldwide have encouraged government retailers to create more job opportunities for domestic populations (Country Profile Series, 2017, p.21). The political risk in Singapore is minimal, and this might be a better opportunity for Tesco to conduct its business in a politically stable environment. The country enjoys political stability in the continent, and it is a democratic country lead by the people.

Economic factors

Economic factors aim at leveling costs, profits, process, and demand and therefore they are the main factors that concern the well-being of TESCO. It is the company to ensure that any possible changes that could occur in policies regarding taxation be investigated properly to ensure that they do not affect the finances of the company. Singapore's economy is growing at a high rate which offers a good opportunity for Tesco to open its stores in the country (Country Profile Series, 2017, p.21). The country has educated and skilled workers which strengthen its economic stability and hence an ideal point for Tesco to expand its markets.

Social factors

Singapore's social life follows the cultures of any Eastern country which guards the traditional family values (Tremewan, 2016, p.19). The younger generation in Singapore tends to follow the Western values and cultures, which could be an advantage for Tesco as they are likely to embrace its products which are mainly motivated by the Western culture. The residents have the materialism feeling that forces them to work hard to fulfill that need hence improving the overall purchasing power of the country (Hill and Lian, 2013, p.27). The above social trends indicate that customers in Singapore have migrated towards bulk shopping. In a bid to counteract the bulk shopping, TESCO has increased

the number of sale for non-food items. Goods and services on demand are likely to be influenced by the beliefs and attitudes of the consumers who could, in turn, be influenced by social conditioning. Over the years, consumers have become more aware of the health issues associated with consumption of inorganic foods, and this has made TESCO adapt and diversify their demand strategies by the sale of healthy organic products.

Technological factors

According to Tsuji (2016, p.45), the technological advancement in Singapore is commendable, and the introduction of internet has worked well to improve access to information in the country. Technological infrastructure is averagely high as about seventy-percent of the households are connected to the internet (Tsuji, 2016, p.51). Technological advancements have been of great significance to TESCO. The forms of technological advancements include the introduction and development of online facilities that could be delivered to customers in their respective homes and secondly, the reduction of labor cost by the introduction of self-service checkout points. Another form of technological advancements has been the investment of energy efficient projects that would reduce the carbon footprint for a very long time.

Environmental factors

Singapore has an environmental control unit that is headed by the Ministry of the Environment and other agencies that are responsible for controlling pollution in the country. The main focus of these bodies is to maintain the quality of air as well the external environment (Ong, 2016, p.378). Tesco should meet all the environmental conservation requirements as stated by the Singapore's legislation.

TESCO has actively participated in the conservation of the environment by minimizing the produced wastes in their stores. The minimization of produced wastes has been

achieved by increasing the level of social conscience among customers. It is the responsibility of the company to address the environmental issues that could be affecting Singapore and later adopts procedures that could help the society in reducing issues such as the increasing carbon footprint. Therefore, Tesco may not face any problems complying with the environmental requirements in Singapore.

Legislative factors

Policies and legislations imposed by the government could impact the performance of TESCO in Singapore. An example could be used in the food retailing commission that suggested the code of practice in companies be introduced to ban malpractices such as demanding payments from suppliers and changing prices of goods without the issuance of notice (Ong, 2016, p.378). Complying with the policies would require TESCO to reduce the prices of goods purchased according to amounts spent on grocery items. Another strategy could be using promotional measures such as price reduction.

Section 2 (Analysis of the company)

In order to understand Tesco's competitive forces in the retail industry, the paper applies the 5-forces analysis. The analysis of the structure of the company is conducted to find its most effective competitive advantage. The five fundamental factors that could be used to identify and evaluate the potential opportunities and threats include competitive rivalry, the threat of new entrants, the threat of substitutes, bargaining power of the suppliers and the bargaining power of the customers (Bob, 2014, p.46). The first three factors could be considered as horizontal competition as the responsible forces operate in a similar way to the market. The last two forces, on the other hand, could be classified as vertical competition as they operate within the supply chain.

The intensity of competitive rivalry

The intensity of competitive rivalry in the TESCO's grocery and food retail industry is high. TESCO faces stiff competition from potential competitors that include Morrison's, Asda, Waitrose and Sainsbury's (Rahman, 2015, p.78). The above companies compete on various aspects which include price variations, customer services, and product promotions. Asda is one of the main competitors has its market share significantly growing together with the other competitors such as Sainsbury and Morrison's. However, the market growth of the competitors is slightly slow to mean that the market rivalry among the competitors has intensified with increased market shares. The increased market shares among the competing rivals have threatened the market leadership position of TESCO. In rural populations, the nearest store could be several miles away, and this could be a discouragement to various primary consumers that later opt for alternatives from retailers such as Co-op and Somerfield. Big discounters like Lidl and Aldi often take over the market in periods of recession (Briaza and Tzezairlidou, 2016, p.117).

Threat of new entrants

The entry of new competitors as a threat in the retail food industry is minimal. The minimal entry of new competitors could be due to the huge capital investment that is required to establish a name and be competitive in the market (Briaza and Tzezairlidou, 2016, p.199). Some of the brands that managed to capture the food retail market included TESCO, Morrison's and Sainsbury's that already occupied about eighty percent of the entire shopping in the UK. To establish a market value, it will require the new entrants to produce goods at exceptionally lower prices or products of higher quality than the competitors. New entrants could also be hindered by barriers such as gaining planning authorization from the government (Moatti, Ren, Anand and Dussauge, 2015, p.751). The entire process could be discouraging as it requires a lot of resources and time to establish.

Threat of substitutes

Substitute products and services as a threat in the grocery retail markets could be medium to high for nonfood items but low for food items. Substitutes for the food retailers in the food retail market are the organic shops, convenience stores and off licenses that are normally not seen as major threats to superstores such as TESCO that provide higher quality products at reasonable prices (Kasemsap, 2016, p. 228). Additionally, TESCO is in a position to get hold of the shops by intentionally opening up stores in cities and towns hence making it difficult for the substitutes to enter the market. However, the threat of nonfood item substitutes such as clothing could be very high making TESCO a threat to the specialty stores.

Bargaining power of suppliers

The suppliers' bargaining power of the industry could be relatively low. It should be noted that vendors are at risk of losing their contracts with big superstores as they are always prejudiced towards major groceries and food. The position of retailers such as TESCO, Sainsbury's and Asda could be strengthened should other retailers lose their contracts with large supermarkets (Kasemsap, 2016, p. 228). The negotiations following the strengthened positions are always positive to acquire the lowest price possible from potential suppliers. Tesco stands a less chance of losing suppliers as it enters the new market as it has a higher bargaining power over the suppliers.

Bargaining power of buyers

The bargaining power of suppliers could be relatively high. The switching cost could be low in instances where products have little differentiation and more standardization resulting to buyers switching from one brand to the other. It has been observed that most customers normally get attracted to the cheapest commodities and with the available retail shops online, product prices could easily be compared for easy selection.

Section 3 (Competitiveness of the Organization)

The competitiveness of the organization can be determined by internally scanning the strategic factors such as critical strengths and weaknesses. The analysis is conducted to determine the extent at which the company is able to take the available opportunities as well as avoiding any possible threat. TESCO has a many strength as well as weaknesses. Some of TESCO's strengths include a strong capital background and stability in income statements, statement of changes in owner's equity, statement of cash flow and balance sheets (Hammad, 2015, p.12). Other strengths include qualified workers in the middle management and favorable economies of scale. Apart from the listed strengths, TESCO also has weaknesses that include a complex company structure that will demand a span of control measures. Another weakness is that employee turn-over could be high at the operational level initiating difficulties in running the company.

The best method that can be used to analyze the strengths and weaknesses of the internal environment of TESCO is the VRIO analysis network. VRIO is an abbreviation of the Value, Rareness, Imitability and organization of the company as Hammad (2015, p.25) explains. The company's value refers to the comparative advantage that the company is likely to yield. The value is considered to be moderate when the same service is offered but in a larger scale. Rareness in the VRIO analysis is used to know how unique the products and services in the company are and whether other competitors in the market have it or not (Stefan and Richard, 2014, p.27). When other competitors in the market also have the same products then it is not considered as being rare. In a competitive market, some producers often try to imitate the goods that other successful companies produce or the services that they provide. For a competitor to be more successful it is important that it has information whether other producers in the market are able to imitate its concept or not (Zurabovna, 2016, p.205). In many cases, imitating the concepts of other companies could be very easy.

The next important step to eradicate the likelihood of imitating the concept is by ensuring that the cost of imitating the concept is very high such that when one has to imitate the product, they have to do so at a very high cost. High cost in imitation eliminates the possibility of competitors imitating the concepts of your company. The last element of VRIO analysis is the Organizational factor. The company has to be well organized if they are to exploit the available resources (Kalyanam, et al., 2015, p.33). Organization starts from the managerial sector to the lowest sector in the company which could include the casual workers. Poor organization will lead to the collapse of the company. All companies want their businesses to thrive and their concepts to be successfully put into practice making them have no choice other than ensuring the best organization for the company.

There are three types of basic organizational structures and they include simple structure, functional structure and the divisional structure. A simple organizational structure has the workers instructionally working below the owner and manager of the company (Kalyanam, et al., 2015, p.33). The functional structure has the top management as the head of the company with the manufacturing department, sales department, finance department and personnel department diligently working under it. The divisional organizational structure is the last and most complicated organizational structure. It is a combination of two subsets of the functional organizational structure. It is headed by the top management and below it are two product divisions both constituting of the manufacturing department, sales department, finance department and the personnel department.

The corporate culture of TESCO could be another internal environmental structure used to analyze the strengths and weaknesses of the company. TESCO believes that a highly organized working system could lead to successful outcomes making the company realize high profits. TESCO also believes that the experiences and skills learnt by the workers could be transmitted from one generation to the other. The beliefs could be a strength used by the company to reach set goals. The company also expects that the orders shall

be literally fulfilled by the micro-management team. The other corporate culture of TESCO is the values that they instil on their staff. The values include personal integrity, customer orientation and honesty. The above corporate cultures could be the strengths of TESCO are properly put into practice but again they could be a major weakness if not put into proper considerations. For efficiency, it is advised that employees' commitment and sense of identity be moderate. The behavioral patterns should also be sustainable with high organizational stability.

Section 4 (Market Entry Method)

From the above analysis, it is clear that Tesco may have a variety of methods that it can use to enter an international market through a strategic expansion approach. For instance, the Tesco can use five entry methods to enter the Singapore market which includes, exporting, licensing, franchising, joint ventures and through wholly owned subsidiaries.

Exporting

Tesco can consider entering the foreign market as an exporting company to feed its consumers in the new market. The main advantage of exporting as an entry method is that it helps in achieving the experience and location economies. Exporting also avoids additional costs that could be used in establishing marketing operations (Hohenthal, Johanson and Johanson, 2014, p.15). However, by using exporting as an entry strategy, the company may face challenges such as tariff barriers, high transportation costs, competition with manufacturers at lower cost locations and lastly there could be a lack of control over the numerous market representatives especially if it is a multi-brand.

Licensing

Tesco PLC. could also use licensing as an entering strategy to the new market in Singapore. Licensing is an agreement that occurs when a licensor grants the licensee the rights to intangible properties such as patents, formulas, trademarks, inventions and copyrights for a specific period in exchange for royalties (Ang, Benischke and Doh, 2015, p.1538). The main advantage of the entry method is that it allows the investors to overcome restrictive investment barriers. The method could also be suitable if the market were unfamiliar. The last advantage is that the development costs could be reduced together with the risk of establishing subsidiaries (Ang, Benischke and Doh, 2015, p.1538). Licensing could be disadvantageous as there could be a loss of control over the used technology which could be overcome by developing a JV and building-up a CROSS-LICENSING. Licensing can lead to the loss of control over activities due to inadequate experience and less coordination internationally.

Franchising

Franchising is another entry method where the franchisor sells intangible properties and in the process, assists the franchisee in doing business but under strict rules. The features of franchising are similar to those of licensing. However, the main disadvantage of licensing is quality control where consumer experiences in one state can affect the experience in another state (Andreu, Claver, and Quer, 2017, p.113).

Joint ventures

Joint ventures entail the establishment of firms that can jointly be owned by two or more independent firms. The merits of the method are that local government aversions can be avoided and the local partner also has information about the market of the host country. Costs and risks could also be shared widely (Sandberg, 2014, p.24). Joint ventures could be disadvantageous because it is less dependent compared to a owned subsidiary. Loss of control over technology could occur resulting in potential conflicts.

Wholly owned subsidiary

The method is considered advantageous due to the tight control of operations and realization of new economies. Over the years, there has been no record of risk associated with loss of competence control. The only disadvantage about wholly owned subsidiary is that the company bears the entire cost as well as risks.

After identifying the market like Singapore, Tesco must accurately determine the time and mode of entry into the market identified. The entry is considered early when an international business becomes first in entering a foreign market before any other foreign firm. However, the entry is considered late when the subjective firm enters the market after other international markets have established and occupied the market (Sandberg, 2014, p.25). Organizations wishing to expand internationally are likely to face issues such as marketing segments, where to obtain products and how to invest. The next step is the evaluation of the best strategy which is done by following three key criteria to success, and they include suitability, feasibility, and acceptability. An entry procedure is considered suitable if it addresses the mission of the company. Feasibility is determined by ensuring that the method chosen can be made to work. The last criteria used to determine success is acceptability, and this is where a company should make sure that all stakeholders accept the entry strategy.

On account, I would suggest TESCO use joint ventures as the most suitable entry method in the international market such as Singapore. Joint ventures could be utilized for a start to get used to the new country's policies and market strategies. After that, TESCO could then exercise the other entry methods such as licensing and franchising. Singapore is a very developed country and so is the market. In most cases, they have strict rules and laws governing the business operations in the country hence making it very difficult for foreign companies and firms to enter the market without legal permission. Singapore has businesses to protect so that foreign investors can not displace them. The whole process makes it difficult to penetrate the market.

The government in Singapore is likely to allow joint ventures as the only entry method into their market for foreign investors. The main reason being that as the foreign investors' profit, they also benefit indirectly. Joint ventures give the Singapore some sort of power to manipulate the market in their favor when the need arises. The method may be the only source of supply for third countries leaving TESCO with no opportunity other than entry through joint ventures. TESCO will most likely benefit from joint ventures as there is joint financial strength giving them a broad base in the capital that is used to invest. The joint venture is the best entry method for TESCO as risks that occur in the line of running the business is shared offering an ability to combine important knowledge about business operations with foreign partners who most likely have the best technological know-how. The joint venture is the most suitable entry method for TESCO when expanding internationally into Singapore's market.

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